

Formation and solution of normal equations for photometry

L Lindegren 1983-08-12

Observation equations

For the photometric solution we have the following unknowns:

- (i) one unknown (x_i) per star ($i = 1$ to n), viz. the magnitude;
- (ii) m global unknowns (y_j , $j = 1$ to m), viz. the "instrument parameters" (a_{00} , a_{01} , etc).

Each observation involves at most one star, but all the global unknowns. Thus, if the observations are numbered $k = 1, 2, \dots$, the k :th observation equation is, after normalization (division by a priori s.d.),

$$p_k x_{i(k)} + q_k' y + (\text{unit variance noise}) = r_k \quad (1)$$

where $i(k)$ is the star involved in observation no. k , and y is the m -vector of global unknowns. p_k , the m -vector q_k , and r_k are computable numbers.

The form (1) is applicable to all kinds of observations. In particular, the a priori magnitude of a standard star is introduced with such an equation in which $q_k = 0$. Similarly, it is possible to give any a priori information on the instrument parameters (y) by means of (at most m linearly independent) equations like (1) with $p_k = 0$.

Formation of normals

The normals become

$$\left(\sum_{k \in i} p_k^2 \right) x_i + \left(\sum_{k \in i} p_k q_k' \right) y = \sum_{k \in i} p_k r_k, \quad i = 1 \text{ to } n \quad (2a)$$

$$(\text{symmetric}) + \left(\sum_k q_k q_k' \right) y = \sum_k q_k r_k \quad (2b)$$

where $\sum_{k \in i}$ stands for a summation over all observations (k) involving star no. i .

The system (2) clearly consists of a diagonal (n,n) -matrix, bordered

to the right by an $(n+m, m)$ -matrix. Since $n \gg m$, the system is very sparse, and it is convenient to represent it by two arrays: an n -vector $\underline{D}$ containing the diagonal, and an $(n+m, m+1)$ -matrix $\underline{E}$ containing the border and, in the last column, the right-hand side (rhs). Thus,

$$\begin{pmatrix} D(1) & & & E(1,1) & \dots & E(1,m) \\ & D(2) & \underline{0} & E(2,1) & \dots & E(2,m) \\ & & \ddots & \vdots & & \vdots \\ & & & D(n) & E(n,1) & \dots & E(n,m) \\ E(1,1) & & \dots & E(n,1) & E(n+1,1) & \dots & E(n+1,m) \\ \vdots & & & \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots \\ E(1,m) & & \dots & E(n,m) & E(n+m,1) & \dots & E(n+m,m) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_n \\ y_1 \\ \vdots \\ y_m \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} E(1,m+1) \\ E(2,m+1) \\ \vdots \\ E(n,m+1) \\ E(n+1,m+1) \\ \vdots \\ E(n+m,m+1) \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$\underline{D}$ and $\underline{E}$ are accumulated as follows (observation index k is dropped from the coefficients p_k, q_k, r_k , and we let r_k be the $(m+1)$:th element of q_k):

```

zero  $\underline{D}$  and  $\underline{E}$ 
for each observation (k)
  i := i(k)
  compute observation equation (p  q1  q2  ...  qm  qm+1 = r)
  D(i) := D(i) + p2
  for j := 1 to m+1
    E(i,j) := E(i,j) + p*qj
    for l := n+1 to n+min(j,m)
      E(l,j) := E(l,j) + ql-n*qj
    next l
  next j
next k

```

Note that the lower-left triangular part of $\underline{E}$ is not used, i.e. the $m(m-1)/2$ elements $E(i,j)$ with $i > n+j$.

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Solution of normals

Direct application of the Cholesky method to the system in (3) leads to the following solution algorithm:

```

for i := 1 to n
    D(i) := 1/SQR(D(i))
next i
for j := 1 to m+1
    for i := 1 to n
        E(i,j) := E(i,j)*D(i)
    next i
    for l := 1 to min(j,m)
        sum := 0
        for i := 1 to n+l-1
            sum := sum + E(i,l)*E(i,j)
        next i
        if (l = j) then
            E(n+l,j) := 1/SQR(E(n+l,j) - sum)
        else
            E(n+l,j) := (E(n+l,j) - sum)*E(n+l,l)
        endif
    next l
next j

```

comment: Cholesky factorization and reduction of rhs completed. Now solve the triangular system:

```

for l := m to 1 step -1
    E(n+l, m+1) := E(n+l,m+1)*E(n+l,l)
    for i := 1 to n+l-1
        E(i,m+1) := E(i,m+1) - E(n+l,m+1)*E(i,l)
    next i
next l
for i := 1 to n
    E(i,m+1) := E(i,m+1)*D(i)
next i

```

comment: solution vector $\begin{pmatrix} X \\ Y \end{pmatrix}$ is now in the (m+1):th column of $\underline{E}$.

Remark: in order to solve the same system with a different rhs (using the previous Cholesky factorization), skip the first three lines (i-loop) and change fourth line to: for j := m to m+1.